

Coffee and Tea?

A comparison of different methods in corpus-based natural language processing on *coffee* and *tea*

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1. Abstract

Coffee and tea have been an integral part of many cultures around the world for centuries, and the words are used widely in everyday life. This paper aims to compare different methods to analyze the words *coffee* and *tea* in a corpus. The methods employed in this study are frequency analysis, Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) (Evert et al. 2016; Church et al. 1990), Log-Likelihood Ratio (LLR) (Gries. 2009; Bybee et al. 2001), colligational analysis using Keyword in Context (KWIC), and Vector Space Model (VSM). Python programming language is used to analyze the dataset from COHA corpus (Corpus of Historical American English) in Google Colaboratory. There is also a brief review of Topic Modeling method applied on GlowBe (Global Online data for Worldwide Behavioral Studies of English).

The comparison reveals that KWIC method provides the most insightful results because it identifies the use of *coffee* and *tea* in the sense of a social gathering. It also shows a specific domain of commercialization where *coffee* is used as in “*coffee* franchise” and “*coffee* stall”, as well as dominant structures in which people usually use *coffee* and *tea*: possessive noun phrases and direct objects. Although there are tools like Antconc, which can help in separating tokens into different positions, colligational method requires the most effort to prepare concordances, and identify, categorize and analyze patterns.

VSM reflects specific social and cultural contexts where *coffee* and *tea* are used. With the associated words like *beer*, *wine*, *liquor*, and *champagne*, it shows the common coffee consumption approach in a social setting where alcoholic drinks are present, and for *tea*, with the associated words like *breakfast*, *supper* and *dinner*, it indicates that tea is usually consumed with meals.

Frequency analysis, PMI, and LLR yield a similar set of collocates, although each method scores and ranks differently. The observations are that PMI underestimates low-frequency collocates like *have* with the score of 0, but it is not found to overestimate high-frequency collocates like *drink* with *coffee* and *cup* with *tea*. In addition, LLR captures approximately 15% more stop-words than PMI. Frequency analysis is the only method that can illustrate the trend of language use over time based on the number of occurrences. It suggests that *coffee* gains more popularity while *tea* sees the opposite.

Lastly, Topic Model appears to be sensitive to the size of the dataset in that it captures many stop words in big datasets. This is an interesting observation because stop words are normally filtered out in the coding process; therefore, they do not show up in a result. In general, however, topic modeling works better with large datasets (Isoaho, Gritsenko & Mäkelä. 2019; Ylä-Anttila. 2016).

2. Methods and Tools

The analysis consists of five parts: frequency analysis, collocation analysis (PMI and LLR), colligation analysis (KWIC), VSM, and Topic Modeling. Frequency analysis examines absolute (or raw) frequency and relative (or normalized) frequency. The search window is set to 5 neighboring words both before and after the target word, and the result filters only the collocates with at least 4 hits. The collocations are demonstrated based on raw frequencies. The strength of the collocations is analyzed using LLR and PMI methods. Punctuations and stop words are removed from the list. In colligation analysis, the words are studied using KWIC method at the positions N-2, N-1, and N+1, e.g. “sip the coffee,” “black coffee,” and “coffee cup” respectively. A vector model calculates the top 30 words with the closest meanings to the target words based on their common semantic features, and Topic Modeling suggests a list of suitable topics for a document based on the weights (frequencies or probabilities) of words.

3. Results

3.1. Frequency Analysis

Picture 1 (left) and 2 (right): The absolute frequencies of *coffee* (left) and *tea* (right) in COHA corpus

Picture 3 (left) and 4 (right): The relative frequencies of *coffee* (left) and *tea* (right) in COHA corpus

Picture 5: A comparison of the relative frequencies of *coffee* and *tea*

Bybee and Hopper (2001) emphasized frequencies as the foundation to studying a language that “It is well known that frequency is one of the most basic measures of linguistic structure, but it is only recently that the importance of frequency has been fully appreciated for the study of language structure and change” (p. 1).

Coffee occurs 242 times in the sample corpus dataset, and *tea* occurs 165 times. The occurrence of *coffee* was the highest in the year 1981 (21 hits) and in 1908 for *tea* (23 hits) (Pictures 1 and 2). When comparing the frequency per year, relative frequency is used because it is a normalized amount of occurrence against the amount of words presented in a specific year. Stefan Gries (2009) elaborates on the significance of relative frequency that “Raw frequencies are by themselves useless; they only become interesting in comparison to other frequencies and contexts” (p. 193). With a generally higher relative frequency, *coffee* is at its peak at a little over 0.0012 while *tea* has an overall lower relative frequency with a peak at only slightly over 0.0004 (Pictures 3 and 4). The trend in Picture 5 shows that *coffee* has been more popular in its usage as *tea* decreases over time. Around the year 2000, both words saw the biggest gap as *coffee* was found 5 times more often than *tea* (0.000125 and 0.000025 respectively).

3.2. Collocation Analysis

POS	<i>coffee</i>	<i>tea</i>
verb	drink(16), pour(10), sip(8), offer(4)	come(6), see(5), give(4)
adjective	hot(7), black(7)	green(4), rice(4)
noun	shop(12), sandwich(6), chair(5), egg(5), pot(5), sugar(5)	cup(21), party(7), afternoon(4)
common	table(9, 5), take(8, 6), serve(5, 4)*	*the frequencies of (coffee, tea)

Table 1: Collocation analysis of *coffee* and *tea* based on raw frequencies

Based on Table 1, the collocates are divided into three categories; verb, adjective, and noun with the frequencies in the parenthesis. The last row is the common collocates that both *coffee* and *tea* share. The result shows that *coffee* collocates more diversely in all categories. It is also associated with the concept of drinking as in *drink*, *pour*, and *sip*, as well as food as in *sandwich*, *egg*, and *sugar*. *Tea*, on the other hand, has a less variety of collocates and is associated with a broader context than being a beverage itself as in *come*, *give*, *party*, and *afternoon*. These collocates of *tea* also portray social interaction and involvement while the ones of *coffee* focus on *coffee* itself as a beverage.

Collocates	PMI (coffee)	LLR (coffee)	PMI (tea)	LLR (tea)
sip	7.8	110.01	0	0
sandwich	7.64	80.44	0	0
cup	7.49	422.43	7.45	274.83
pot	7.04	60.78	0	0
tea	6.88	94.74	0	0
shop	6.65	136.64	0	0
pour	6.57	112.12	0	0
sugar	6.45	54.8	0	0
egg	6.23	0	0	0
drink	6.12	165.39	0	0
hot	5.82	67.85	0	0
roll	5.2	0	0	0
serve	5.02	0	5.18	33.64
table	4.9	70.71	4.69	37.2
black	4.87	54.47	0	0

Collocates	PMI (coffee)	LLR (coffee)	PMI (tea)	LLR (tea)
chair	4.8	0	0	0
offer	4.5	0	0	0
take	3.26	0	3.24	0
have	0	135.69	0	76.61
catnip	0	0	10.29	82.4
beef	0	0	7.11	49.16
rice	0	0	6.99	48.19
coffee	0	0	6.88	94.74
afternoon	0	0	5.43	35.59
green	0	0	5.39	35.26
party	0	0	4.98	56.08
come	0	0	3.14	0
give	0	0	3.12	0
when	0	0	3.05	0
see	0	0	2.92	0

Table 2: Collocation analysis of *coffee* and *tea* based on PMI and LLR scores

The number of observations is capped at top 30 based on their PMI and LLR score separately. During the pre-processing phase, the calculation of LLR captures a lot more stop-words than PMI (53.33% compared to 36.67% for *coffee* and 60% compared to 46.67% for *tea*). This finding is in accordance with Stefan Evert and Andrew Hardie (2010) who state that “The LLR statistic is known to capture more stop-words than other association measures like MI or t-score” (p. 193).

Both PMI and LLR methods yield a similar set of words demonstrated in Table 1. However, there are some observations which reflect the characteristics of the methods as follow.

Have has low frequencies as it does not appear in Table 1, which shows the most frequent collocates, and *have* also scores 0 in PMI method. This observation agrees with what Stefan Th. Gries states in 2013 that “PMI can underestimate the strength of association for low-frequency co-occurrences” (p. 122).

Drink, on the other hand, is a frequent collocate for *coffee* and *cup* for *tea* as in Table 1. The PMI score of *drink* with *coffee* is 6.12 and *cup* with *tea* is 7.45, which when compared to the PMI score of other collocates, is not an overestimation. This finding goes against Gries (2009) and van Eijnatten and Huijnen (2021), who suggest that PMI can overestimate the strength of association between words that frequently appear together in a corpus. It is interesting that this finding does not apply with *table*, which is also a commonly frequent collocate for *coffee* and *tea*. *Table* gets a balanced score in both PMI and LLR methods, consistent with its frequency in Table 1.

3.3. Colligation Analysis

N-2

At N-2 level, *tea* has been frequently found to be used as a meal some people eat in the late afternoon and consists of food such as sandwiches and cakes, with tea to drink (Collins English Dictionary, n.d.); for example, to the *tea*, returned to *tea*, walk after *tea*, and at a *tea*. *Tea* is also associated with a variety of words related to food, such as breakfast and *tea*, coffee or *tea*, and chocolate or *tea*. Lastly, tea is found to be used as a direct object with a determiner, e.g. sipped his *tea*, poured the *tea*, and made his *tea*.

For *coffee*, the dominant structure portrays different ways of consuming, preparing, and interacting with coffee, and *coffee* is used as a direct object of a verb, such as stir his *coffee*, tasted the *coffee*, and enjoyed fresh *coffee*. It is also associated with other foods and drinks in the construction X and/or *coffee* as in sugar and *coffee*, wine or *coffee*, and sandwiches and *coffee*. In addition, similar to *tea*, *coffee* is used in the sense of a social gathering at which coffee and other refreshments are served (Collins English Dictionary, n.d.); for example, invitations for *coffee*, began with *coffee*, and bonding over *coffee*. The construction X of coffee is also identified, e.g. pots of *coffee*, sips of *coffee*, and trifle of *coffee*.

N-1

At N-1 level, tea has been often found with a variety of modifiers describing type, preparation, or serving of tea as in iced *teas*, China *teas*, and afternoon *tea*. Another dominant structure is the possessive noun phrases, e.g. his *tea*, that *tea*, and their *tea*. Lastly, *tea* occurs with a verb and without determiners, such as have *tea*, sipped *tea*, and drinking *tea*.

In this level, *coffee* is found most often with modifiers that describe time of day (breakfast *coffee*, midnight *coffee*), location (motel *coffee*, local *coffee*), and types or flavor (wheat *coffee*, blend-of-the-day *coffee*). Moreover, a variety of adjectives are present describing the temperature, appearance, or quality of coffee like strong *coffee*, organic *coffee*, and steaming *coffee*. Less dominant structures are verb + *coffee* and possessive noun phrases as in drink *coffee*, make *coffee*, produce *coffee*, and his *coffee*, your *coffee*, their *coffee* respectively.

N+1

At N+1 level, *tea* is found to modify another noun that indicates social aspect (*tea* party, *tea* meetings, *tea* dances), preparation and brewing (*tea* leaves, *tea* kettles), break and relaxation (*tea* break, *tea* time), and the context in which tea is consumed (*tea* plantations, *tea* ships, *tea* cups).

Similarly, *coffee* takes the same role as a modifier describing functionality (*coffee* cup, *coffee* pot, *coffee* mugs), physical attributes (*coffee* grounds, *coffee* brown), and commercialization (*coffee* franchise, *coffee* stall, *coffee* workers).

3.4. Vector Space Model

Shifting from frequency-based methods to a semantic-feature-based vector space model, the closer the score of the words to 0, the closer their meanings are to the target word. We cap the results at 30 closest words. The result shows that both *coffee* and *tea* share the closest meaning with other food-and-drink words, but the scores of neighboring words of *tea* are higher indicating less semantic similarity; for example, *wine* (0.23, 0.28), *beer* (0.24, 0.40), and *sandwich* (0.27, 0.35). *Coffee* conveys a similar meaning with a wider type of words, such as verbs like *drink* (0.27), *sip* (0.30), *pour* (0.37), and nouns like *bottle* (0.31), *lunch* (0.34), and *cup* (0.39). It is interesting that *dinner* (0.36) and *supper* (0.46) show up in the list for *tea* but not *coffee* while *lunch* (0.34) shows up in the list for *coffee* but not for *tea*. In addition, apart from *wine* and *beer* mentioned above, *coffee* encircles more alcoholic words like *liquor* (0.34) and *champagne* (0.35).

The last two observations suggest that *coffee* and *tea* are associated with different social and cultural contexts as noted by Turney (2010) that “Vector space models can be used to represent the meanings of words and phrases in natural language. The models can be used to identify associations between specific words and concepts” (p. 141). The prevalence of alcoholic words in the coffee-related associations may reflect the common consumption of coffee in social settings where alcohol is also present. Conversely, the appearance of *dinner* and *supper* in tea-related associations may indicate that tea is often consumed during or after meals, particularly in certain cultures.

This method, however, does not capture the use of *coffee* and *tea* in the sense of a social gathering, which has been found commonly and as one of the dominant structures in colligational analysis. This issue is also encountered in the work of Rheault and Cochrane (2019) as they explain “Despite their ability to identify associations between specific words and ideological positions, vector space models may struggle to capture the full complexity of ideological language use, especially when it comes to the connotations, implications, and historical references of certain terms” (p. 161).

Overall, the first two findings resonate with the results from frequency, collocation, and colligation analysis. A vector space model, however, enables a more sophisticated interpretation of the results. This is noted by Turney (2010) that “Vector space models can be used to capture subtle differences in meaning that may not be apparent from frequency counts alone. This is because the models take into account the distributional information of the words, which reflects how they are used in context.” (p. 141).

3.5. Topic Modeling

This method is sensitive to the size of datasets. For a large topic size starting from around 200,000, many stop words come up very high in the list occupying around the first 10 suggested topics. In contrast, for a small topic size (not over 2,000), the method suggests more content words.

4. Summary and Discussions

This paper compares frequency analysis, PMI, LLR, KWIC, VSM, and Topic Modeling methods to analyze the words *coffee* and *tea* in a corpus. Frequency analysis shows that *coffee* appears more often in the corpus while *tea* occurs less frequently over time. Collocation analysis reveals that when compared to *tea*, *coffee* collocates more diversely in all kinds of words including verbs. *Tea*, on the other hand, is often used in the context of social interaction and involvement. Colligational analysis reflects the usage of *tea* and *coffee* in the sense of social gathering. They are commonly used together with food-and-drink related words. They are often used in possessive noun phrases and as a direct object. Colligational analysis confirms the previous finding that *coffee* collocates with a wider range of modifiers including a category that are not found to co-occur with *tea* like commercialization. VSM gives more intuitive results showing that *coffee* has more alcoholic drinks as its semantic neighbors while *tea* has meals as a company. Lastly, Topic Modeling is found to capture a lot more stop-words in large datasets.

This study also identifies some conflicts on the characteristics of PMI and LLR methods, which may arise from the fact that the size of the dataset is relatively small. For future research with a larger dataset, concordance analysis can be done using a visualization tool like Tableau, which allows for more robust and statistical-based results.

5. References

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Appendix

Python code on Google Colaboratory

- Frequencies:
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1YVocI3gA0bB5dG4hvF2vJoN7cMqIH1fD?usp=share_link
- Collocations and concordances:
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1IWwtqrSM0mdVjuuh7kVk2cGgO7wwd1Ce?usp=share_link
- Vector Space Model:
https://colab.research.google.com/drive/10Qs_GaWCxvq5O_XbeAe8LKsynKoXdgeo?usp=share_link
- Topic Modeling:
<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1mhosmanUkLAc2vjBJT055CjRTxwIA4J-?usp=sharing>

Frequency Analysis

Collocates	Coffee	Tea
catnip	32	4
drink	16	0
shop	12	0
pour	10	0
table	9	5
take	8	6
sip	8	0
tea	8	0
black	7	0
hot	7	0
sandwich	6	0
serve	5	4
chair	5	0
egg	5	0
pot	5	0
sugar	5	0
offer	4	0
roll	4	0
cup	0	21
coffee	0	8
party	0	7
come	0	6
see	0	5
afternoon	0	4
beef	0	4
give	0	4
green	0	4
rice	0	4

PMI and LLR

Collocates	PMI (coffee)	LLR (coffee)	PMI (tea)	LLR (tea)
sip	7.8	110.01	0	0
sandwich	7.64	80.44	0	0
cup	7.49	422.43	7.45	274.83
pot	7.04	60.78	0	0
tea	6.88	94.74	0	0
shop	6.65	136.64	0	0
pour	6.57	112.12	0	0
sugar	6.45	54.8	0	0
egg	6.23	0	0	0
drink	6.12	165.39	0	0
hot	5.82	67.85	0	0
roll	5.2	0	0	0
serve	5.02	0	5.18	33.64
table	4.9	70.71	4.69	37.2
black	4.87	54.47	0	0
chair	4.8	0	0	0
offer	4.5	0	0	0
take	3.26	0	3.24	0
have	0	135.69	0	76.61
catnip	0	0	10.29	82.4
beef	0	0	7.11	49.16
rice	0	0	6.99	48.19
coffee	0	0	6.88	94.74
afternoon	0	0	5.43	35.59
green	0	0	5.39	35.26
party	0	0	4.98	56.08
come	0	0	3.14	0
give	0	0	3.12	0
when	0	0	3.05	0
see	0	0	2.92	0

Vector Space Model Score of *Coffee*

Coffee	similarity score
coffee	0
wine	0.22681344
beer	0.24219819
drink	0.26523884
sandwich	0.26887201
soup	0.282042
tea	0.29676829
sip	0.30174076
bottle	0.31136479
chocolate	0.31258136
bread	0.33600043
liquor	0.33688942
cream	0.33922058
lunch	0.34452896
champagne	0.34646225
breakfast	0.34695957
cake	0.34922326
pour	0.36575008
bowl	0.3702724
spoon	0.37372821
sugar	0.3757404
eat	0.37613496
butter	0.38880304
egg	0.38960842
pot	0.39071569
spill	0.39207772
cup	0.39476377
meal	0.39505042
potato	0.40267438
dish	0.41153455

Vector Space Model Score of *Tea*

Tea	similarity score
tea	0
wine	0.28820634
soup	0.29260229
coffee	0.29676829
chocolate	0.31333955
bread	0.34183418
sandwich	0.34704446
dinner	0.35895186
butter	0.36446912
bean	0.36693277
potato	0.37948378
cream	0.38703596
breakfast	0.38896009
bowl	0.39953128
cake	0.4021755
egg	0.4054156
beer	0.40593583
drink	0.41749432
cheese	0.42017714
pot	0.42848778
rice	0.43083397
sugar	0.44471934
beef	0.44521158
cup	0.44665275
sour	0.44744904
cook	0.45558528
milk	0.45577601
meal	0.46046655
supper	0.4607093
eat	0.46231647

Concordances of *Coffee*

Lines / Positions	N-5	N-4	N-3	N-2	N-1	N0	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
1	vinyl	chair	and	was	served	coffee	by	a	clerk	.	
2	waitress	arrives	.	 	EDDIEJust	coffee	,	black	.	.	
3	drop	of	rich	cream	mellows	coffee	.	Maybe I			
4	of	shade	trees	.	Glossy-lea ved	coffee	s	bent	under	their	
5	with	which	to	stir	his	coffee	.	I hope			
6	Strange	poured	a	cup	of	coffee	from	the	thermos	he	
7	the	fat	--	and	drink	coffee	.	741350	That	a	
8	,	those	earrings	under	your	coffee	table	--	it	was	
9	in	his	chair	,	a	coffee	cup	on	the	table	
10	kept	in	his	car	.	Coffe e	was	okay	for	times	
11	.	She sipped the				coffee	.	Happy to			
12	.	Veronica sipped her				coffee	.	@	@	@	
13	He glanced around the					coffee	shop	,	then	leaned	
14	they	'd	gone	out	for	coffee	a	few	times	.	
15	doing	a	surveilla nce	,	because	coffee	went	through	him	too	
16	other	fibres	,	tobacco	,	coffee	,	tea	,	cocoa	
17	and	a	warm	dish	of	coffee	for	the	Sultana.	--	
18	brackish	bayou	water	to	make	coffee	.	We	talked	with	
19	by	night	,	and	endless	coffee	...	<p>	Commenc ement	,	
20	of	sugars	,	tea	,	coffee	@	@	@	@	
21	went	into	a	Raklios	for	coffee	.	I	started	to	
22	Sec	,	he	drank	his	coffee	and	smoked	his	own	
23	to	the	bouleva rd	,	black	coffee	laced	with	brandy	,	
24	are	children	is	fruit	,	coffee	for	the	father	and	
25	on	the	porch	for	our	coffee	.	I	have	n't	
26	the	luxuries	of	sugar	and	coffee	;	and	in	addition	
27	legs	into	the	kitchen	for	coffee	.	Sharon	was	there	
28	she	has	tasted	Odo	's	Coffe e	pot	.	--	Kil	

29 After being plied with hot **coffee** and gruel the young
 30 sugar and cream in that **coffee** , Parkins -- want it
 31 in his cabin or drinking **coffee** with his shipmates at
 32 Would you care for **coffee** or tea ? I
 33 eggs on toast , and **coffee** ; mademoi
 selle is served
 34 had any dinner , only **coffee** and sandwich
 es at odd
 35 , and a cup of **coffee** , and an ashtray
 36 moist . He sipped his **coffee** . Dubin then put
 37 needed . Strange tasted the **coffee** . Janine had brewed
 38 Eddie are finishing their breakfast **coffee** . Sarah is in
 39 NICK ARROYO / StaffReg ular Firenze **Coffe** custo
 mer Peter Smith enjoys
 40 interludes with her , having **coffee** , discussin
 g horses ,
 41 fried an egg and made **coffee** to get her off
 42 Hilla Becher lay on his **coffee** table . Anderson 's
 43 set up with pastry and **coffee** . The play had
 44 1957 , 618150 <p> The **coffee** break is being re-defin
 ed
 45 about half the world 's **coffee** , was paying dividen
 ds
 46 of purchasing larger amounts of **coffee** than she could use
 47 while he was taking his **coffee** and thus had the
 48 and parked behind Chester 's **Coffe**
 e Shop . In the
 49 to pour into lady 's **coffee** or the lady 's
 50 . The waitress brings the **coffee** . EDDIE (
 51 . Dark chocola
 te variations include **coffee** and nib brittle .
 52 and she could make some **coffee** , too . Strange
 53 thing . How 's the **coffee** ? Delicious
 54 Perhaps we who never drink **coffee** can hardly understand the
 conversatio
 n
 55 , after 11 pots of **coffee** and much more
 56 and later , took longer **coffee** and lunch breaks ,
 57 into a drawer . **Coffe**
 e ? said
 Kitty

58 , for neither tea nor **coffee** was introduced till about

59 . Mrs. Sloan offered him **coffee** , drew him into

60 excepting the hot food (**coffee** , hot milk ,

61 in her . Ruth drew **coffee** , and as she

62 when you 've had your **coffee** . One hundred thousand

63 @ @ @ tea and **coffee** ; and , moreov
er

64 goodbye . They sip their **coffee** in silence for an

65 took a chair across a **coffee** table from him .

66 How about some more **coffee** in the den ?

67 transgenic caffeine-loaded soybean to produce **coffee** in Minnesota , the

68 grease , tea leaves , **coffee** grounds , etc .

69 said as he sipped his **coffee** . Neither did

70 beans , sweet potatoes , **coffee** , bread liberally spread

71 ! I thought I smelt **coffee** . Just what I

72 phial into the pot of **Coffee** . Odo . Odo

73 coffee in Minnesota , the **coffee** workers of Kenya are

74 everyone 's protests on making **coffee** and eating the remains

75 Development Authority . Photo : **coffee** cup 705450 This is

76 Just a few sips of **coffee** , and already he

77 little as she poured the **coffee** and the first citizen

78 trucker who was drinking midnight **coffee** late in April 1989

79 for the day , while **coffee** s were up 7

80 extra glasses for milk , **coffee** cups , two spoons

81 after the inevitable service of **coffee** , the housewife was ready

82 down in her robe for **coffee** with Dubin if she

83 at 12:15 , a free **Coffee** Concert is held ;

84 of eggs and bacon , **coffee** , cinnamon rolls ,

85 sandwich and a cup of **coffee** . You want something
 86 were sitting around the Sheraton **coffee** shop with Hans Christ
 87 Brad Glidden insisted she have **coffee** first , so she
 88 , so she was drinking **coffee** and eating stuffed grape
 89 from the wreck . Get **coffee** and blankets and -- and
 90 , looking up from his **coffee** , which he was
 91 his ^{**30;3046;TO} OLONG in the motel **coffee** shop in San Jose
 92 and I were having our **coffee** . Bebb said ,
 93 , or into bananas and **coffee** ? a kind of
 94 , for a cargo of **coffee** . - Vol.
 95 We 'll solve this over **coffee** and dessert .
 96 of proliferating places offering \$4 **coffee** drinks , there is
 97 future . By the time **coffee** was served his head
 98 King novel down on the **coffee** table , went over
 99 of imports of rubber , **coffee** , nitrates , iodine
 100 last of all with the **coffee** pot . The light
 101 Trevor , word for **coffee** and privacy in this
 102 . She returns to her **coffee** . Eddie keeps looking
 103 you something ? Drink ? **Coffee** ? CHARLIEI do
 104 groping for his cup of **coffee** . Martini tossed a
 105 He started with a nickel **coffee** stall during the Chicag
 106 blue turtleneck sweater had a **coffee** stain over one breast
 107 Kuroki , having arrived with **coffee** and sandwiches , paused
 108 piece . He enjoyed fresh **coffee** , putting on a
 109 Every morning in cafes and **coffee** shops around the country
 110 watched as a ^{Veronic} arranged the **coffee** ^{servic} e on a rolling
 111 me just a handful of **coffee** , master @ @
 112 cost of the sugar and **coffee** which we furnish the
 113 while her ^{colleague} office s sip **coffee** at their desks ,
 114 a sugar refinery or a **coffee** proce plant to take

ssing

115	the	tables	drinking	wine	or	coffee	and	eating	@	@
116	you	a	cup	of	hot	coffee	.	That	'll	make
117	He	drove	to	a	nearby	coffee	shop	and	they	settled
118	have	n't	tasted	tea	or	coffee	for	four	months	!
119	devoured	the	woman	.	When	coffee	had	been	served	,
120	were	hot	,	creamy	,	coffee	tasty	.	Mt	.
121	time	the	last	cup	of	coffee	is	poured	,	they
122	conciator y	,	-	especiall y	towards	coffee	.	If	you	could
123	a	cup	of	steaming	black	coffee	.	Molly	had	a
124	.	The	linoleum	floors	had	coffee	stains	;	vinyl	chairs
125	Knitting	Club	,	bonded	over	coffee	,	conversa tion	and	skeins
126	Molly	had	a	cup	of	coffee	for	herself	too	,
127	Jenkins	shrugged	,	drank	his	coffee	and	said	into	the
128	,	a	salad	and	black	coffee	.	She	was	n't
129	.	Two	steamin g	cups	of	coffee	splatt ered	against	the	wall
130	know	--	I	made	her	coffee	--	and	I	saw
131	for	a	second	cup	of	coffee	and	to	shave	.
132	dime	for	a	cup	of	coffee	.	I	said	,
133	got	up	to	pour	hot	coffee	for	them	,	and
134	paper	pads	scattere d	across	the	coffee	table	.	He	told
135	slopped	over	with	mud	and	coffee	groun ds	,	this	one
136	@	@	press	agent)	coffee	.	Next	to	come
137	on	hard	tack	and	muddy	coffee	,	and	the	odor
138	the	web	and	nursing	a	coffee	and	doughnut	.	As
139	pouring	a	fresh	cup	of	coffee	.	Now	,	
140	've	just	bought	into	a	coffee	shop	in	the	mall
141	able	to	get	some	real	coffee	!	-	perhaps	
142	,	handing	him	a	steaming	coffee	.	Your	spies	
143	ranged	from	light	tan	to	coffee	brown	.	But	all
144	cigarettes	over	second	cups	of	coffee	and	everybod	lingered	at

							y		
145	her	custom	,	had	her	coffee	in	her	room)
146	George	's	dogged	s	for	coffee	,	a	drink ,
147	stay	home	,	but	the	coffee	shop	had	endowed Maxine
148	The	man	runs	a	local	coffee	franch ise	,	a modest
149	and	takes	with	him	the	Coffe e	for	the	Sultana .
150	a	manager	of	a	local	coffee	shop	and	subsequen tly bought
151	for	Martha	Graham	,	fashioning	coffee	cups	for	his kitchen
152	a	cholesterol-lad en	meal	with	black	coffee	.	<p>	In Carrolt on
153	.	The	days	began	with	coffee	and	bloody	marys and
154	instalment	of	buttered	rolls	and	coffee	would	be	served with
155	Just	a	cup	of	black	coffee	,	please	.
156	underpaint ed	.	I	splashed	some	coffee	on	the	canvas to
157	beard	into	which	egg	and	coffee	invari ably	de	? scende d
158	rice	,	dates	,	and	coffee	.	The	very poor
159	butts	in	cuspido rs	,	of	coffee	and	meat	and beer
160	in	the	morning	to	drink	coffee	.	I	barged in
161	never	offer	a	cup	of	coffee	to	a	policeman when
162	wait	until	we	have	our	coffee	and	you	gentlemen have
163	is	staring	down	into	a	coffee	cup	.	Aunt Polly
164	to	stain	it	.	Blend-of-th e-day	coffee	from	the	place where
165	sir	.	Black			coffee	is	the	only thing
166	--	View	page	rying	a	coffee	pot	,	but he
167	England	.	291150	Like	the	coffee	or	tea	break in
168	covered	with	her	gs	--	coffee	,	extra	sneakers ,
169	told	him	as	they	had	coffee	at	the	counter .
170	ca	n't	I	get	my	coffee	hot	?	
171	after	pouring	second	cups	of	coffee	,	asked	him what

172 @ @ @ was having coffee in the Sheraton Hotel

173 mask the blemishes on a coffee barge with palm trees

174 house-boy spills a cup of coffee on him , and

175 accept an invitation to drink coffee at his colleagues '

176 two and a cup of coffee and then , after

177 , sat with cigarettes and afterward as the tempo

178 the shell to clear the coffee . In the same

179 heard the watchword , coffee and privacy .

180 hunched shadows as she poured coffee and passed out menus

181 you like something in your coffee ? Veronica asked

182 men had had sandwiches and coffee sent up ; plates

183 essences , citrus drinks and coffee ; in Atlanta .

184 army correspondent has since reported coffee made at the South

185 all offers of pastry or coffee . They looked wary

186 She had another cup of coffee and a cigarette with

187 flowers , sit in a coffee shop , and get

188 uses of a stimulant . Coffee has been priceless to

189 hurried to pour him some coffee and set a chair

190 @ will come out . Coffee , Fruit . Lay

191 of a saucer and keeps coffee mugs refilled continuously .

192 a few drops into her coffee , just in sport

193 , a cup of strong coffee , or some other

194 down and have some fresh coffee sent up . Servants

195 elsewhere . She strained the coffee , humming a tune

196 now the color of creamed-up coffee , dull in the

197 roasted , and flavored with coffee ; while a friend

198 tray) p. 5 WAITER Coffee and English ? MARG E

199 bread , Dutch cheese , coffee . She had not

200	sandwich	and	gulp	of	tepid	coffee	and	wandere d	along	the
201	Latte	:	8	ounces	brewed	coffee	.	1-Apr	cup	light
202	trade	,	not	with	their	coffee	sham	bas	paying	off
203	it	would	n't	.	The	coffee	s	come .	@	@
204	up	the	coast	and	had	coffee	and	sandwich es	at	Malibu
205	her	maid	had	brought	her	coffee	,	and	with	it
206	toast	,	and	emptied	his	coffee	cup	.	It	was
207	the	counter	,	refilled	a	coffee	cup	,	came	back
208	All	I	want	is	some	coffee	.		Well	
209	leading	articles	of	export	are	coffee	,	cocoa	,	hides
210	British	aristocracy	was	taking	his	coffee	in	solitude	at	the
211	pemmican	,	so	that	the	coffee	of	a	regiment	may
212	Nicaragua	from	a	one-crop	(coffee)	country	into	an
213	from	Greek	.	We	drink	coffee	first	grown	in	Ethiopi a
214	give	our	friend	here	some	coffee	,	while	I	show
215	:	How	about	some		coffee	?	Christa	went	
216	a	quick	snack	and	some	coffee	before	I	took	a
217	diluted	with	a	trifle	of	coffee	.	And	still	further
218	at	six	forty-fiv e	.	The	coffee	shop	opened	at	six-thirt y
219	never	coming	in	?	-	coffee	is	stone	cold	.
220	but	bacon	and	eggs	and	coffee	.	She	had	forgotte n
221	,	the	color	of		coffee	with	rather	thin	cream
222	.	Paul	and	Marge	with	coffee	.	Caf	noises	.
223	.	Kennyp170sc owled	moodily	into	his	coffee	cup	.	Jen	@
224	aside	disconsolately	,	and	drank	coffee	d	instea .	Well	
225	,	into	his	almost	empty	coffee	cup	--	slipped	from
226	.	Sarah	pours	him	some	coffee	,	and	he	tries
227	ham	,	butter	,	and	coffee	.	The	same	meal
228	and	put	them	on	the	coffee	table	.	Sorensen	began
229	his	feet	up	on	a	coffee	table	and	closed	his

230	are	grown	(like	organic	coffee)	in	the	shade
231	@	@	SAMPLER	<p>	FIRENZE	COFFEE	<p>	*	VIBE :
232	the	graves	with	flowers	in	coffee cans	;	the	waist-high
233	by	even	larger	trays	bearing	coffee in	little	cups	.
234	he	was	breakfasting	in	the	coffee shop	he	read	in
235	'd	had	three	cups	of	coffee and	a	notable	homemade
236	for	him	;	there	was	coffee ,	but	no	spoon
237	took	another	sip	of	the	coffee .	The	problem	
238	the	wholesome	article	is	wheat	coffee .	I	have	lately
239	not	an	ordinary	breakfast	of	coffee ,	rolls	,	omelette
240	the	battered	Salvadoran	economy	.	Coffee	,	traditionally	the
241	will	chat	and	take	our	coffee .	By	the	way
242	patiently	wipes	up	the	spilled	coffee .	Dissolve	to	:

Concordances of *Tea*

Lines / Positions	N-5	N-4	N-3	N-2	N-1	N0	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
1	the	scene	of	the	Boston	Tea	Party	to	put	up	
2	.	He	drank	several	iced	teas	,	snorted	nose	spray	
3	Oh	,	here	's	our	tea	.	It was			
4	brew	herself	a	cup	of	tea	and	deeply	breathed	above	
5	to	go	back	to	the	tea	.	Nora	was	very	
6	Casa	Bonita	for	late	afternoon	tea	.	On	the	following	
7	.	She	was	probably	having	tea	with	Mrs.	Philip	Courtney	
8	nationality	;	she	would	have	tea	with	the	Turks	and	
9	warm	up	a	cup	of	tea	by	the	energy	leaking	
10	morning	paper	over	breakfast	and	tea	.)	The	newspaper	
11	milk	.	My	breakfast	and	tea	,	with	bread	,	
12	picture	as	you	are	.	Tea	?	-	-	Not	a
13	cups	.	Lydia	tasted	the	tea	,	nodded	her	approval	
14	,	brown	rice	and	green	tea	.	It was			
15	bathe	again	,	and	after	tea	went	back	to	the	
16	would	be	served	on	the	tea	cart	,	set	at	
17	,	tobacco	,	coffee	,	tea	,	cocoa	,	rice	
18	,	as	he	returned	to	tea	from	a	stroll	with	
19	import	more	of	sugars	,	tea	,	coffee	@	@	
20	,	was	their	dish	of	tea	.	But	it	fitted	
21	had	seen	done	in	the	tea	plantations	;	in	playing	
22	do	n't	come	to	a	tea	she	is	giving	to	
23	@	@	not	your	China	teas	atp236al	.			
24	poured	her	a	cup	of	tea	she	talked	at	length	
25	had	been	invited	to	take	tea	with	the	Ervengs	that	
26	ready	for	a	cup	of	tea	when	I	came	back	
27	you	care	for	coffee	or	tea	?	I	'd	recommend	
28	at	a	reception	,	or	tea	,	or	some	such	

29 ? I 'd recomme
nd the **tea** . We make it
 30 his mother a cup of **tea** , - - I suspect
 31 There would be scones for **tea** and little pots of
 32 the old days appeared for **tea** ; and he and
 33 and former receptio
ns , or **teas** , or r whateve
the
 34 honey . The **tea** sounds fine .
 35 a whole bucketfu
l of catnip **tea** alongsid
e , and the
 36 of Tiptree jam . The **tea** parties of Mr. Benings
en
 37 bombing . As Bobby sipped **tea** , and the Presiden
t
 38 kitchen with mother , having **tea** . He let
 39 brew you a cup of **tea** myself . Ever since
 40 poured the first cup of **tea** , her father and
 41 as yet , for neither **tea** nor coffee was introduc
ed
 42 , and a cup of **tea** with real cream ,
 43 @ @ @ @ @ **tea** and coffee ; and
 44 touched nothin ' but his **tea** , an ' I
 45 glass is easily washed . **Tea** Table . Afternoo
n tea
 46 @ @ @ @ of **tea** ? But I
 47 in the quiet walks after **tea** the face of the
 48 so well . We had **tea** in the cosiest little
 49 . Tea Table . Afterno
on **tea** is often served in
 50 bringing with it grease , **tea** leaves , coffee grounds
 51 ? But I despise **tea** , so I answe
d
 52 the kettle . While the **tea** steeped , Papa stropped
 53 than sororitie
s and gowns and **teas** . And in this
 54 swapping sugar for sausage
s and **tea** for butter and eggs
 55 us come over and take **tea** , etc . Hilliard
 56 stuck his finger into his **tea** and stirred the ice

57	three	pence	a	pound	on	tea	;	it	requires	one
58	want	any	of	their	old	tea	,	and	I	'd
59	people	.	I	gave	her	tea	,	sweetm eats	and	cakes
60	and	had	some	with	his	tea	.	He	wet	and
61	with	'	em	frolicking	,	tea	partying	,	excursio ning	,
62	softly	,	Finish your			tea	,	young	man	,
63	of	the	package deal	that		teas	recently	propose d	for	selling
64	anybody	to	come	to	their	teas	.	I	've	got
65	gossip flows like sweet					tea	,	Vonda Thayer		
66	to	be	brought	out	at	tea	time	.	The	tea
67	.	One	evening	,	at	tea	,	I	was	conversi ng
68	,	when	they	had	high	tea	@	@	@	@
69	at	tea	time	.	The	tea	tray	,	with	every
70	anybody	else	.	There	were	teas	in	Washing ton	Square	,
71	tale	.	He	sipped	his	tea	,	and	Margare t	rose
72	,	with	every	furnishin g	for	tea	on	it	,	will
73	's	going	to	give	a	tea	and	wants	us	all
74	soy	milk	and	Celestial	ngs	teas	to	Terra	and	Garden
75	that	with	mamma	.	After	tea	Nora	played	;	I
76	waited	until	the	children	's	tea	was	over	.	They
77	the	taste	of	oranges	and	tea	and	some	kind	of
78	to-morrow	at	five	and	have	tea	.	Down	in	
79	local	writers	such	as	Michelle	Tea	,	Peter	Plate	and
80	at	the	table	,	drinking	tea	out	of	a	big
81	their	grasp	.	The		tea	party	's	spilt	,
82	@	@	to	give	a	tea	!	-	-	and the
83	of	a	kingdom	to	a	tea	meeting	,	there	are
84	do	with	the	price	of	tea	in	Telegu	?	Silvery
85	I	took	him	up	some	tea	and	toast	,	- -

86 appetite . A cup of **tea** , such as Mrs.
 87 @ @ @ , and **tea** . Before , my
 88 when he returned to the **tea** table he sat down
 89 she had heard . The **tea** to which Jack and
 90 plan for a Rosebud **Tea** , in spite
 91 ! I have n't tasted **tea** or coffee for four
 92 salmon , nor , at **tea** , currants with cream-to
 93 her daughter 's friends to **tea** ; and it had ast
 94 was the life of the **tea** table . Her wit
 95 already drank more cups of **tea** with your friends than
 96 there were solemn , stately **tea** s drinking among the upper
 97 for more honey with your **tea** ? Miss Perumal
 98 @ @ @ @ @ **tea** ships came only to
 99 when the hour arrived for **tea** , the young deserter
 100 the far side of the **tea** cart , and he
 101 Oaklands , where an occasio nal **tea** party will be the
 102 his manager , rang for **tea** but , knowing no
 103 previously seen . I saw **tea** cups as frail looking
 104 Rice sails for AmeT ' **tea** -- @ @ @
 105 when they hurried to their **tea** . Lighting a cigar
 106 with a swallow of cold **tea** and hurried to join
 107 good crop they bought Chinese **tea** , the Chinese demand
 108 at the piano , played **Tea** for Two , got
 109 The gong pealed out that **tea** was ready , and
 110 served him neither rice nor **tea** , and had ignored
 111 of society women at afternoo n **tea** , the talk of
 112 with you at Ruth 's **tea** ? It was
 113 invitation to Miss MacFarla ne 's **tea** . Ah ,
 114 @ busy washing -- most **tea** time -- he !
 115 and Brownie both had iced **tea** , and I joined
 116 day I saw them at **tea** at the Beau Rivage
 117 would have a cup of **tea** and such other comforts

118 Reuben Plonsky . Spilling **tea** in Boston Hobber ?

119 of the town : hence **teas** , receptio
ns , opera

120 told me that his class **teas** called up and he

121 it , at these same **teas** , to know what

122 astrologer , a lady with **tea** leaves , a man

123 Reynolds to make some beef **tea** . She will keep

124 291150 Like the coffee or **tea** break in the West

125 these mild voices and tinkling **tea** cups . The lazy

126 @ @ @ @ @ **tea** . That depends

127 chamber music at lunch , **tea** dances , swing bands

128 together over a cup of **tea** , and Barker was

129 raw starch . Chocolat
e or **Tea** . Sprinkle with borax

130 lazy charm of the laden **tea** table , the deep

131 Garry . Now
serve **tea** , Parkins . Come

132 teakettle . Mother likes **tea** in the late afternoon

133 really not your cup of **tea** , Willie .

134 Felicia had selected for her **tea** to Ruth , and

135 , red wine and green **tea** , have turned the

136 not thought of when the **tea** was first discussed -- includin
g

137 . On fond . On **tea** . On sending even

138 what was my cup of **tea** . Captain Thiele turns

139 Fairies of the Hupeh **tea** plantation , who had

140 been feigning than of the **tea** and bread and butter

141 people in the world but **tea** kettles ; no mouths

142 to pick 1,102 lbs. of **tea** leaves a day .

143 and take a cup of **tea** and some crackers .

144 's place and poured the **tea** . I was thankful

145 brew her a cup of **tea** . As he was

146 pyramid . Ditto for green **tea** . But when scientist
s

147 . While she sipped her **tea** she said : '

148 and adopted in Arabia , **tea** discover in China ,

ed

149	have	my	bitters	and	catnip	tea	regular	.	But	if
150	had	stooped	to	please	.	Tea	was	brought	,	and
151	cutting	,	like	a	hybrid	tea	.	I	believe	there
152	Rocky	Smalt	,	at	a	tea	party	,	taking	hold
153	not	the	maker	of	her	tea	.	--	Kil	.
154	risk	;	those	in	green	tea	may	fight	heart	disease
155	making	beef	broth	,	beef	tea	,	scraped	beef	and
156	do	not	care	for	the	tea	parties	here	,	Mr.
157	wo	n't	ask	me	to	tea	,	because	I	'm
158	The	strobe	lights	made	his	tea	black	skin	radiate	with
159	used	to	be	seen	at	tea	under	the	trees	in
160	@	@	@	@	@	tea	Dinner	Seared	Ginger	Tuna
161	a	practice	as	the	early	tea	in	the	tropics	before
162	's	easy	done	without	catnip	tea	;	it	do	n't
163	prepared	,	a	cup	of	tea	,	for	instance	,
164	@	to	get	my	catnip	tea	and	bitters	regular	--
165	take	a	second	cup	of	tea	?	indicating	thereby	

Topic Modeling (Large Datasets)

topic size: 429450.4092437946

Suggested Words	Score	Suggested Words	Score
nan	72161.68	blob	0.99
the	24465.4	app	0.99
be	15156.83	rider	0.99
a	11901.59	frequency	0.99
to	11256.33	interface	0.99
of	9986.84	windows	0.99
and	9234.81	flickr	0.99
in	6083.77	artery	0.99
you	4078.66	velocity	0.99
for	3675.28	byte	0.99
that	3658.52	algorithm	0.99
it	3509.34	bug	0.98
have	3502.74	herpes	0.98
this	3217.66	disk	0.98
on	3104.41	header	0.98
with	2837.5	upload	0.98
as	2754.46	chelsea	0.98
can	2491.96	desktop	0.98
we	2253.93	microsoft	0.98
your	2102.64	exhibition	0.98

topic size: 371924.08433772076

Suggested Words	Score	Suggested Words	Score
nan	78142.48	raka	0.99
the	22295.2	pleasurable	0.99
be	11922.39	dhamma	0.99
of	11051.37	pg-13	0.99
and	10054.42	wicket	0.99
in	8023.77	bismarck	0.99
a	7161.72	ats	0.99
to	6979.04	bowling	0.98
have	3146.49	phuket	0.98
with	2688.23	arahant	0.98
for	2514.33	palace	0.98
as	2468.3	ml	0.98
on	2272.19	clive	0.98
by	2066.43	prince	0.98
's	2005.7	belfast	0.98
that	1938.71	contemplation	0.98
at	1857.59	mindfulness	0.98
it	1833.65	ghanim	0.98
from	1827.03	fe	0.98
he	1635.82	orca	0.98

Topic Modeling (Small Datasets)

topic size: 1495.3000145366968

Suggested Words	Score	Suggested Words	Score
therapist	0.1	muted	0.02
muted	0.1	compass	0.02
compass	0.1	greenish	0.02
greenish	0.1	7,000	0.02
obstruct	0.1	self-righteousness	0.02
witty	0.1	maximal	0.02
patricia	0.1	extravagant	0.02
7,000	0.1	2009-2010	0.02
self-righteousness	0.1	devour	0.02
270	0.1	pronunciation	0.02
maximal	0.1	authenticate	0.02
extravagant	0.1	alphabet	0.02
ceramics	0.1	botanic	0.02
2009-2010	0.1	rift	0.02
oct	0.1	screenshot	0.02
devour	0.1	rhythmic	0.02
pronunciation	0.1	schooler	0.02
dylan	0.1	luminous	0.02
alphabet	0.1	toshiba	0.02
authenticate	0.1	reposition	0.02

topic size: 1568.0061385503964

Suggested Words	Score	Suggested Words	Score
chrome	13.05	proton	0.85
google	11.12	chrome	0.72
browser	6.39	beam	0.21
therapy	6.37	amy	0.19
proton	5.1	facilitator	0.18
beam	4.97	2017	0.18
patient	3.68	buckingham	0.16
amy	2.91	nhs	0.13
extension	2.51	metropolis	0.13
outline	1.96	browser	0.13
firefox	1.7	accompanying	0.13
recently	1.31	therapy	0.1
facilitator	1.1	christie	0.1
christie	1.1	firefox	0.09
buckingham	1.1	steadily	0.09
2017	1.07	thriving	0.09
nhs	1.07	revamp	0.08
metropolis	1.06	nationally	0.06
overtake	1.04	google	0.06
nationally	1.03	overtake	0.05